

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Germany: An Introduction

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The most important form of participation in political decision-making at local level is the active and passive voting right, especially the election of the local council (municipal or county council) or the election of the mayor or county administrator. While individuals naturally run for office in mayoral/county administrator elections, lists of the local divisions of the political parties active nationwide dominate in local council elections. Elections at the local level are regulated in the respective Local Code (Municipal or County Code) and in the respective Local Election Law (*Kommunalwahlgesetz*). The constitutional basis therefore is Article 28(1)(2) of the Basic Law (BL), according to which 'the people' are also to be found in the 'counties and municipalities (...) must have a representation which has resulted from general, direct, free, equal and secret elections' (electoral principles). There are great differences in the individual countries in the definition and design of the respective electoral system. Complicated mixing systems have arisen here within the scope defined by Article 28(1)(2) BL. The principle of the proportional representation system, in which the seats are distributed in proportion to the votes cast for the nominations, is consistently practiced. In numerous *Länder*, however, this has been supplemented by personnel elements (e.g. Baden-Württemberg with a so-called 'favorites list' / 'diversion'). The system of majority voting, in which applicants run directly against each other and the one with the highest number of votes wins the seat, is only envisaged under strict conditions, especially if one or no list has been submitted. In the various countries, either the d'Hondtsche method or the Hare / Niemeyer method or the 'divisor method with standard rounding' according to Sainte-Laguë / Schepers are used in the calculation.¹⁶⁸ In various *Länder*, attempts have been made to introduce a blocking clause in order to avoid splitting the municipal councils into many small groups and to ensure their functionality. However, under the current framework conditions, the Federal Constitutional Court considered this (especially the 5 per cent clause) to be a violation of the principle of equal election.

The citizens of the respective local government are entitled to vote and are therefore holders of an active right to vote. Citizens are all residents of a local government who are entitled to vote in local elections in accordance with the provisions of the respective Local Election Law. Accordingly, citizens are all Germans (Article 116 BL) or EU foreigners, provided that they are residents (main residence) in the local government (municipality/county) concerned for between 16 days and six months (depending on *Länder* law) and have reached the age of 16 or 18 (also depending on *Länder* law). The provisions on the right to stand as a candidate

¹⁶⁸ Comparative Bernd Grzeszick and Jochen Rauber, 'Reformoptionen für die Sitzzuteilung in kommunalen Vertretungskörperschaften' (2018) 149 BayVBI 577.

(eligibility for election, also passive right to vote) are linked to this, but in some cases provide for a longer period of residence in the local government's territory and/or a higher age. After the conclusion of the Maastricht Treaty in 1992 and the introduction of citizenship of the Union, the constitution was supplemented by Article 28(1)(3) BL. It states that 'persons who are nationals of a Member State of the European Community' are 'entitled to vote and to be elected in elections in counties and municipalities' in accordance with the law of that state.

But it is becoming increasingly difficult for parties to recruit committed political personnel for local political mandates and offices. Particularly in rural small local governments, where local politics is based purely on volunteer work (with at least an expense allowance),¹⁶⁹ the parties often fail to fill the election lists with suitable candidates. The reasons for this are the burden of bureaucracy and the very high expenditure of time involved. At the same time, local politicians see themselves exposed to incitement and hostility in the increasingly coarse interactions in the society which can have both psychological and physical effects. Especially the honorary mayor's office represents a great challenge with regard to the compatibility of work and family.

While no plebiscitary elements are provided for in the Basic Law at the level of federal policy, they play a major role at the local level. Extensive regulations have been created in the local regulations of all *Länder*, some of them only in the recent past. Both the names and the requirements vary depending on the *Land*, but are comparable across the board. In addition to the voting right(s), the citizens of a local government are entitled to plebiscitary possibilities such as the citizens' proposal (*Bürgerantrag*), the citizens' assembly (*Bürgerversammlung*) and the citizens' petition (*Bürgerbegehren*) aimed at the implementation of a referendum (*Bürgerentscheid*). With the citizens' proposal, citizens can request that the local council deals with a specific matter while leaving its decision-making powers untouched. The citizens' assembly cannot make a decision, it can only make proposals and give suggestions. Through the citizens' petition, the citizens of a local government can request that they decide on a matter of the local community themselves instead of the local council. This gives them additional room for participation in terms of political organization. Nevertheless, the local council remains the guiding body of the representative democracy at the local level, which is why various requirements are placed on the admissibility of a citizens' petition and large areas of local policy are excluded from the citizens' petition (or referendum). If the local council declares the citizens' petition admissible, the content of the question must be engaged with. In a local council meeting it is therefore necessary to decide whether the content of the citizens' petition should be complied with. If the local council makes this decision, a referendum will not take place and the further legal situation results from the relevant local

¹⁶⁹ Three out of four mayors in cities and towns with a size of 2,000 or more exercise their office full-time. 25% are honorary mayors. However, due to the widely differing regulations and exceptions to differentiate between full-time and – if at all provided – voluntary work in the individual *Länder*, in-depth analyzes are not possible and that's why there are no reliable numbers existing.

council decision. If the council does not comply with the admissible citizens' petition, a referendum must be made within a certain period.

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